

FAUNA OF THE VESPID WASPS FAMILY (VESPIDAE) IN UZBEKISTAN

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Vespidae, belonging to the Hymenoptera order, is one of the largest families in this order in terms of their number. The family is divided into several species, ranging from solitary to gregarious (Prezoto, 2007). They belong to the family of true wasps (Vespidae), with 5,274 species in 256 genera and 6 subfamilies (Kurzenko, 2012, Antropov et al, 2017). Previously, they were grouped into three subfamilies: Vespidae, Masaridae, and Eumenidae. Today, all true wasps are grouped into the subfamilies Euparagiinae, Masarinae, Eumeninae, Stenogastrinae, Vespinae and Polistinae belonging to the Vespidae family (Kurzenko, 2012, Carpenter, 1981). The first three subfamilies are exclusively solitary insects, while the last three are gregarious wasps. In Russia, the subfamilies Eumeninae, Masarinae, Polistinae, and Vespinae make up the fauna of this family.

Studies of the fauna of the family of vespidea wasps were carried out in various biotopes of all natural and anthropogenic territories of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2025. As a result of the analysis of the results of the conducted research, 35 species and subspecies belonging to 20 genera and 3 subfamilies of the Vespidae family were identified (Table 1). The systematic status and faunal data of the identified species are presented below.

The identified species were classified into 3 subfamilies (Eumeninae, Polistinae, Vespinae) of the Vespidae family. Regarding the distribution among subfamilies, the Eumeninae subfamily was the leader with 28 species (80%), the Vespinae subfamily was the second with 5 species (14.3%), and the Polistinae subfamily was the third with 2 species (5.7%) (Table 1).

Table 1.

The species composition of the Vespidae family identified in Uzbekistan during our research

Family	Subfamily	Genera	Species
Vespidae	Eumeninae	<i>Ancistrocerus</i> Wesmael, 1836	<i>Ancistrocerus parietum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
		<i>Antepipona</i> de Saussure, 1855	<i>Antepipona barrei</i> (Radoszkowski 1893)
			<i>Antepipona deflenda</i> Sauders, 1853
			<i>Antepipona specifica</i> (Morawitz 1895)
		<i>Chlorodynerus</i> Blüthgen, 1951	<i>Chlorodynerus arenicola</i> (Kostylev, 1935)
			<i>Chlorodynerus incisipes</i> (Kostylev, 1935)
		<i>Eumenes</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Eumenes mediterraneus</i> Kriechbauber, 1879
			<i>Eumenes sareptanus</i> André, 1884
			<i>Eumenes separatus</i> Gusenleitner, 1972
			<i>Eumenes coarctatus lunulatus</i> Fabricius, 1804

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	<i>Euodynerus</i> Dalla Torre, 1904	<i>Euodynerus strigatus</i> Radoszkowski 1893 <i>Euodynerus rufinus</i> Blüthgen, 1942
	<i>Eustenancistrocerus</i> Blüthgen, 1938	<i>Eustenancistrocerus askhabadensis</i> (Radoszkowski, 1886) <i>Eustenancistrocerus amadanensis</i> (de Saussure, 1856)
	<i>Jucancistrocerus</i> Blüthgen, 1938	<i>Jucancistrocerus consimilis</i> (Morawitz, 1895) <i>Jucancistrocerus tachkendensis</i> (Dalla Torre, 1889) <i>Jucancistrocerus atrofasciatus</i> (Moravitz, 1885)
	<i>Katamenes</i> Meado Waldo, 1910	<i>Katamenes dimidiatus</i> Brulle, 1832
	<i>Knemodynerus</i> Blüthgen, 1940	<i>Knemodynerus excellens</i> (Pérez, 1907)
	<i>Odynerus</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Odynerus melanocephalus</i> (Gmelin, 1790)
	<i>Onychopterocheilus</i> Bluthgen, 1955	<i>Onychopterocheilus fausti</i> (Moravitz, 1873)
	<i>Paravespa</i> Radoszkoowski, 1886	<i>Paravespa quadricolor</i> (Moravitz, 1885)
	<i>Pseudepipona</i> Saussure, 1856	<i>Pseudepipona herzi</i> (Morawitz, 1895) <i>Pseudepipona herrichii</i> de Saussure, 1856 <i>Pseudepipona kostylevi</i> Fateryga, 2022
	<i>Symmorphus</i> Wesmael, 1836	<i>Symmorphus murraris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Tachyancistrocerus</i> Giordani Soika, 1952	<i>Tachyancistrocerus schmidti</i> (Kokujev, 1913)
	<i>Xanthodynerus</i> Blüthgen, 1954	<i>Xanthodynerus dentipes</i> (Kostylev, 1940)
Polistinae	<i>Polistes</i> Latreille, 1802	<i>Polistes dominula</i> Christ, 1791 <i>Polistes watti</i> Cameron 1900
Vespinae	<i>Vespa</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Vespa orientalis</i> Linnaeus, 1771
	<i>Dolichovespula</i> Rohwer, 1916	<i>Dolichovespula sylvestris</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
	<i>Vespula</i> Thomson, 1869	<i>Vespula germanica</i> Fabricius, 1793 <i>Vespula rufa</i> Linnaeus, 1758 <i>Vespula vulgaris</i> Linnaeus, 1758
Total:	3	35

When the species ratio, belonging to the genera of the Vespidae family, was studied, it was determined that 4 species (11.4%) belong to *Eumenes* genera of the Eumeninae subfamily, 3

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species (8.6%) belong to *Antepipona*, *Pseudepipona*, *Jucancistrocerus* and *Vespula* generas, 2 species (5,7%) belong to *Euodynerus*, *Eustenancistrocerus*, *Chlorodynerus* and *Polistes* generas, as well, one species (2,8%) belong to *Ancistrocerus*, *Katamenes*, *Knemodynerus*, *Odynerus*, *Onychopterocheilus*, *Paravespa*, *Symmorphus*, *Tachyancistrocerus*, *Xanthodynerus*, *Vespa*, *Dolichovespula* generas.

According to the results of field studies conducted in 2020-2025 and an analysis of literature spanning almost 150 years, the number of species identified to date in the natural and anthropogenic territories of Uzbekistan is 122.

Thus, it was determined that the true wasps in the fauna of Uzbekistan consist of 122 species belonging to 6 subfamilies and 38 genera. The species *Jucancistrocerus atrofasciatus* (Moravitz, 1885) was recorded for the fauna of Uzbekistan for the first time.

In conclusion, during field studies conducted in 2020-2025, 35 species and subspecies of the Vespidae family, 3 subfamilies, 20 genera, were found in various biotopes of all natural and anthropogenic territories of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In studies of true wasps in Uzbekistan, which have a history of almost 150 years, based on the analysis of about 40 literature data by 22 researchers and the results of our own research, it was noted that the Vespidae family consists of 122 species belonging to 6 subfamilies, 38 genera. During the studies, the species *Jucancistrocerus atrofasciatus* (Moravitz, 1885) was recorded for the fauna of Uzbekistan for the first time. Of the total 122 identified species, 37 species were recorded by only one author. Another 85 species were cited in the works of two or more authors.

References

1. Antropov, A.V. & Fateryga, A.V. (2017) Family Vespidae. In: Lelej, A.S., Proshchalykin, M.Yu. & Loktionov, V.M. (Eds.), Annotated Catalogue of the Hymenoptera of Russia. Vol. 1. Symphyta and Apocrita: Aculeata. Proceedings of the Zoological Institute RAS, Supplement 6, pp. 175–196. <https://doi.org/10.31610/trudyzin/2017.supl.6.5>
2. Carpenter J.M. (1981). The phylogenetic relationships and natural classification of the Vespoidea (Hymenoptera) // Systematic Entomology. – V. 7. – P. 11–38.
3. Kurzenko N.V. (2012) Family Vespidae – Fold-winged Wasps. Annotated Catalog of Insects of the Russian Far East. – Hymenoptera, Vol. I. – Vladivostok: Dalnauka. – 423 p.
4. Morawitz, F. (1895) Materialien zu einer Vespidenfauna des Russischen Reiches. Horae Societatis Entomologicae Rossicae, 29 (3–4), 407–493.
5. Prezoto F., Sabino J. Giannotti E. & Nascimento F.S. (2007). Entre mandíbulas e ferrões: O estudo do comportamento de vespas. // As distintas faces do comportamento animal Campo Grande: UNIDERP. – P. 43–45.